

Deliverable 6.2

Interim report on Dissemination, exploitation and communication

Version 2

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Executive summary

This interim report outlines the project's dissemination, exploitation, and communication efforts to date. We have made significant progress in raising awareness and engaging stakeholders through workshops, participation in events and publications, particularly in social media. Our focus is on optimizing outcomes and maximizing the impact of our project.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leaders

1. Introduction

Communicating a project is essential to maximize its impact from the beginning of its implementation. In this report, the communication efforts within GRINNAQUA are explored, assessing current strategies, their effectiveness and outcomes.

2. Communication channels

2.1. Traditional media

During the first 17 months of the project, both the GRINNAQUA coordinator and project manager gave an **interview** to the Climate Global News Magazine on the project goals and the path to reach them. The news piece was titled “How CIIMAR’s Initiatives Are Advancing Sustainable Aquaculture Through Innovative Green Strategies for Animal Health Management” (Fig.1) and is freely available online.

Climate Global News is a magazine directed at the general public, designed for environmentally conscious individuals which can include scientists, activists and policymakers who wish to be up-to-date on climate-related news, initiatives and innovations.

The reach of the interview was maximized by sharing it on the project website and social media of both GRINNAQUA, the Aquatic Animal Health team's social media and CIIMAR’s social media. The interview can be read at: <https://climateglobalnews.com/how-ciimars-initiatives-are-advancing-sustainable-aquaculture-through-innovative-green-strategies-for-animal-health-management/>

Fig. 1: Interview on GRINNAQUA at Climate Global News Magazine

2.2. Website

A project website (grinnaqua.eu) (Fig. 2) was created at the beginning of the project and has been fed with all the content coming from GRINNAQUA, including news, events, publications and resources (including communication resources and learning materials).

The website has been constantly updated and currently counts 18 news pieces, 2 newsletters, learning materials for the two first workshops and communication materials such as the project flyer, business card and poster. The website also includes the work description and the consortium with links to the project partners' websites and links to the projects' social media and newsletter subscription link.

Fig. 2: an overview of the news tab of the project website

The funding is carefully announced on the website's footer, according to the rules described in the GA (Fig.3)

Fig. 3: Website's footer, with the funding acknowledgement.

2.3. Social media

Social media accounts have been created for the GRINNAQUA project, including [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#) and, more recently, YouTube. These are fed exclusively with content from the project development. The community following these accounts has been increasing steadily and with it our posts' reach. Currently, with 136 followers on Twitter and 644 connections on LinkedIn, each post is reaching on average 300 accounts on Twitter and 2 000 accounts on LinkedIn.

The posts on both accounts are often shared by the different institutions' accounts, their teams and members. Both social media accounts include a short funding acknowledgement in the cover image (Fig. 4 & 5)

Fig. 4: GRINNAQUA Twitter profile with short funding acknowledgement in the cover picture

Fig. 5: GRINNAQUA LinkedIn profile with a short funding acknowledgement in the cover image.

The project's YouTube channel was created recently, once the materials for workshops 1 and 2 became available for upload. Though created less than 3 weeks ago, the videos are already reaching over 40 views. Funding is now acknowledged in the account as it is individually

acknowledged at the end of each video (Fig. 6), to account for the possibility of embedding the resource on other platforms.

Fig. 6: Funding acknowledgement at the end of each GRINNAQUA YouTube video.

These communication efforts contributed to **KPI 8** “Number of project-related social media posts” and **KPI 9** “Social media reach. Number of visualizations per post (average) throughout the project”. Please see section 4 for a summary of KPI measures.

2.4. Newsletter

Efforts to build a newsletter audience started soon after the project implementation. However, building an audience from scratch takes some time. For this reason, the release of the first newsletter was delayed, to make sure our efforts had a proportionate impact. Two newsletters were released since, following the plan, and the third one is currently being prepared.

The [first newsletter](#) (Fig. 7), released in July, was sent to 45 subscribers. Out of these, 36 opened the newsletter. Following its release, the newsletter was shared within the institutions’ communication channels and shared on social media, which amounted to 38 more opens, and our audience reached the USA, UK, Romania, Spain, Greece, Italy, Norway and Sweden. This showed us that although people are not very receptive to subscribing to newsletters, its reach can be more than doubled by other, parallel, efforts.

Fig. 7: First GRINNAQUA newsletter, released in July 2023

The [second newsletter](#) (Fig. 8) was released in October. It was a short one, which we considered as an extra issue, as its goal was just to communicate news about a new workshop which had not been included in the previous issue. This issue was sent to an audience of 52 and was opened by 56 readers.

Fig. 8: Second GRINNAQUA newsletter, released in October 2023

GRINNAQUA funding is acknowledged at the bottom of the newsletter, according to the GA.

3. National events

3.1. General public events

On the 15th of October, Sergio Fernandez Boo gave a talk on marine bivalve cultivation at Serralves, a foundation where CIIMAR often contributes to talks to the general public. Although the main objective of his talk was not to communicate GRINNAQUA, he took the opportunity to introduce the project and connect with the public to get the general public's view on aquaculture products. A questionnaire was shared with the participants (Fig. 9) and the results are discussed in Deliverable 2.3.

Fig. 9: A questionnaire to gather the opinions of the general public on aquaculture products was distributed in Serralves during a session where Sergio Fernández Boo gave a talk about marine bivalve cultivation.

3.2. Academic events

Mariana Vaz, GRINNAQUA technician, as a former student of the Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, took the opportunity to communicate the project at an open class on the 19th of April 2023 (Fig. 10). Participants in the open class were mostly students involved in degrees and masters related to marine resources and biotechnology. As this event was not organized by the GRINNAQUA team, no information about participation is available.

Fig. 10: Open class at the Polytechnic Institute of Leiria by GRINNAQUA technician Mariana Vaz.

3.3. Industry events

3.3.1. XXIII Seminário de Aquacultura

The Aquaculture seminar, organized by the Portuguese Aquacultures Farmers Association is an industry meeting that gathers national practitioners. The goal of this association is to highlight the benefits of aquaculture, promote economic growth and promote responsible and sustainable production of high-quality fish. 90% of practitioners in the aquaculture sector are represented by this association.

The XXIII Aquaculture seminar (*Seminário de Aquacultura*) (Fig. 11), took place on the 26 of May 2023 in Setúbal, Portugal.

XXIII SEMINÁRIO DE AQUACULTURA
26 DE MAIO 2023
ESCOLA HOTELARIA E TURISMO DE SETÚBAL

Programa

10:15 - 10:20 Sessão de abertura pela APA	12:15 - 12:30 Projeto Comunicação - APA Artur Costa (CoLab + Atlantic)
10:20 - 10:50 Sessão de abertura Ministra da Agricultura e Alimentação Maria do Céu Antunes e SEPescas, Teresa Coelho	12:30 - 14:15 ALMOÇO Degustação produtos de aquacultura
10:50 - 11:20 Programa Mar 2030 Dina Ferreira (AG Mar2030)	14:15 - 16:30 World Café - "A aquacultura para o futuro que queremos" Associados + CoLabs B2E, +Atlantic, S2AQUA, GreencoLab e Forum Oceano
11:20 - 11:45 Controlo Norovírus nas ostras: A importância da análise laboratorial na prevenção dos surtos. Daniela Silva (ALS Portugal)	16:30 - 17:00 Discussão dos resultados e Encerramento Associados+ CoLabs B2E, +Atlantic, S2AQUA, GreencoLab e Forum Oceano
11:45 - 12:15 Projetos IGNITION e GRINNAQUA Benjamin Costas (CIIMAR)	INSCRIÇÕES https://forms.gle/g3cUv4HMbarCbE8p8

grinnaqua IGNITION ALS mar 2020 PORTUGAL 2020 União Europeia

Fig. 11: Program for XXII Aquaculture Seminar, organized by the Portuguese Aquaculture Association.

During this seminar, Benjamin Costas, GRINNAQUA coordinator, had the opportunity to communicate the project to the participants (Fig. 12) and explain how their opinion was needed and how they could provide it through an online questionnaire. Afterwards, during the networking session, the team (Fig. 13) contacted the practitioners individually to reinforce this request.

Fig. 12: Benjamin Costas, the GRINNAQUA coordinator, communicated the project to aquaculture practitioners during the XXIII Aquaculture Seminar.

Fig. 13: GRINNAQUA team, Benjamin Costas, Marina Machado and Rita Azeredo at the XXIII Aquaculture seminar

GRINNAQUA's participation in this event was publicized on social media and in a Spanish industry online magazine, "mis-peces": <https://www.mispecies.com/noticias/Asociacion-Portuguesa-de-Acuicultura-celebrara-el-26-de-mayo-su-XXIII-Seminario/> Indicating that this event has not just a National but an Iberian reach.

These efforts to gather the points of view of aquaculture practitioners were, however, unsuccessful, with practitioners indicating it would be easier to get their feedback if the questionnaire was shared in paper instead of online. Nevertheless, an unfruitful effort to send out the questionnaire by email was still made.

3.3.2. XXIV Seminário de Aquacultura

Based on this feedback, the GRINNAQUA team participated in the following edition of the seminar, on the 3rd of November 2023, in Setúbal (Fig. 14). A physical version of the questionnaire was shared with most participants, but only 3 responses were gathered. More information about this effort is available in Deliverable 2.3.

Fig. 14: Participants in the XXIV Aquaculture seminar, on the 3rd of November 2023.

3.4. GRINNAQUA workshops

3.4.1. Workshop 1. Increasing researchers' skills on the use of -omics tools in studies of disease resistance

The first GRINNAQUA workshop, organized by the Roslin Institute / The University of Edinburgh, was hosted by CIIMAR on the 16th and 17th of March 2023.

The workshop counted 47 applicants, all of them from academia, with different background levels. Because this workshop was very practical and would require one-at-one help to overcome any obstacles during the practical session, the course had to be limited to 30 participants. These were selected based on the usefulness of the workshop goals on their current and future work, while maintaining the group as diverse as possible. The participants (Fig. 15) were mostly postdocs and PhD students but included MSc students.

Fig. 15: Participants in the first GRINNAQUA workshop, on “Increasing researchers’ skills on the use of -omics tools in studies of disease resistance”, on the 17th of March 2023.

The agenda and all materials from the workshop can be found on the [GRINNAQUA website](#). Out of the 30 participants, 16 provided anonymous feedback on the course quality and fit to their expectations. Overall, participants were very pleased with the quality of the course, its duration, the support material provided and the overall usefulness of the newly acquired skills (Fig. 16)

Fig. 16: Participants feedback on the course content, duration, material provided and usefulness, where 1 is “strongly disagree” and 5 is “strongly agree”

Participants were equally happy with the teachers’ proficiency and ability to convey their knowledge (Fig. 17)

Fig. 17: Participants feedback on the course teachers, where 1 is “strongly disagree” and 5 is “strongly agree”

The same level of approval was expressed for the adequateness of the venue and fitness of the food to everyone’s needs. (Fig. 18)

Fig. 18: Participants feedback on the venue and food options, where 1 is “strongly disagree” and 5 is “strongly agree”

We received only one suggestion for improvement for this workshop:

- Great event perfectly orchestrated by an outstanding team!
- Next time maybe one extra day would be helpful. Learning with an example as the organizers did was helpful, but an extra day to repeat a full RNASeq analysis would be perfect!

3.4.2. Workshop 2. Granting researchers with increased knowledge on fish vaccination

The second GRINNAQUA workshop, on fish vaccination, was organized by CSIC and hosted by CIIMAR, in Porto, on the 18 and 19th of October.

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The workshop received 58 applications, attracting not only academia, with different background levels but also practitioners.

This workshop was divided into theoretical and practical sessions, which, due to their nature, had different capacities and applicants could choose to participate in the theoretical alone were they not selected to participate in the whole workshop. Participants' selection was based on the usefulness of the workshop goals on their current and future work while trying to maintain a diverse group in terms of background and gender (Fig.19). 30 participants were selected for the full workshop and an extra 12 were able to participate in the theoretical session alone (Fig- 20).

Fig.19: Background of participants in the second GRINNAQUA workshop

Fig. 20: Participants in the 2nd GRINNAQUA workshop

The agenda and all materials from the workshop can be found on the [GRINNAQUA website](#).

Out of the 40 participants, 20 provided anonymous feedback on the course quality and fit to their expectations.

Overall, participants were very pleased and considered the quality of the workshop as very high, particularly in terms of its duration, the support material provided and the overall usefulness of the newly acquired skills (Fig. 21).

Fig. 21: Participants' feedback on the course content, duration, material provided and usefulness, where 1 is "strongly disagree" and 5 is "strongly agree"

Participants were also very pleased with the teachers' ability to convey the subjects (Fig. 22)

Fig. 22: Participants feedback on the teachers' proficiency and capacity to communicate the content, where 1 is "strongly disagree" and 5 is "strongly agree"

Our efforts to ensure everyone was comfortable and able to find food fitting to their needs was also recognized by the participants (Fig. 23)

Fig. 23: Participants feedback on the venue and dietary options, where 1 is “strongly disagree” and 5 is “strongly agree”

The open question where participants could offer suggestions to improve our workshops was met with really nice and supportive messages:

- You are an amazing team.
- Thank you for organizing this wonderful workshop, I'm looking forward to seeing you all soon.
- I would like to congratulate and thank all the GRINNAQUA team for the excellent workshop.

3.4.3. Intellectual Property Course. 1st module: Protection and valorisation

In collaboration with the Horizon2020 project BlueBio4Future and the Science and Innovation Office a CIIMAR, an extra workshop was prepared in the context of GRINNAQUA, as it was well aligned with the project’s goal of capacitating CIIMAR to raise staff’s research profile and increase its innovation capacity. We set an initial limit for participants at 30, but because the demand was so high we arranged to raise our capacity to 45 people, but had to close registration 2 weeks in advance. The course took place on the 31st of October 2023.

Due to the nature of this course and because it counted on the support from partner institutions (CSIC) and a company specialized in patents in science, no materials are available. Nevertheless, the full agenda and teachers' profiles are available on the [GRINNAQUA website](#).

We sent out an anonymous form to evaluate the course the day after but were able to collect feedback from 6 participants only.

The participants were overall very happy with the course content and organization (Fig. 24)

Fig. 24: Participants' feedback on the workshop's overall quality.

As well as with the structure, content and duration of the course, and with the teachers' proficiency in the topic and ability to communicate it (Fig. 25).

Fig. 25: Participants feedback on the workshop structure, content and teachers

Overall the participants found the content of the workshop useful for their future work (Fig. 26).

Fig. 26: Participants' feedback on the workshop's usefulness for their future work.

None had any suggestions for improvement.

3.5. International conferences

3.5.1. European Maritime Day

Every year, the European Maritime Day is the meeting point for European maritime actors, where everyone has the opportunity to engage and outline joint actions for the future of the blue economy. The 2023 edition, organised by the European Commission, the City of Brest, the Region of Brittany, the Department of Finistère and the General Secretariat for the Sea, took place in Brest, France. With this year's edition focusing on themes such as “new approach to a sustainable blue economy” and “innovation in the blue economy”, this was a perfect opportunity to showcase GRINAAQUA. We took this opportunity by setting up a stand (Fig. 27), where GRINNAQUA scientist Lourenço Pinto was able to connect and network with a wide array of ocean actors, including industry leaders, experts and NGOs, sharing the project's goals and plans and starting conversations which may hopefully lead to future collaborations.

Fig. 27: GRINNAQUA business stand at the European Maritime Day

3.5.2. 21st International Conference on Disease of Fish and Shellfish

GRINNAQUA was one of the exhibitors at the 21st International Conference on Disease of Fish and Shellfish, held from 11 to 14th September in Aberdeen, UK. Communication on the project, including the work planned under the project and the impact we expect to have in aquaculture science as well as in the business sector, was supported by the project poster, flyers and business cards. The conference, mostly directed at academia, was a great opportunity to connect with other scientists in the area and explore the possibility of future synergies. The team (Fig. 28) took the opportunity to have a progress meeting at the site, allowing for an in-person meeting without adding to the project's carbon footprint.

Fig. 28: GRINNAQUA team at the 21st International Conference on Disease of Fish and Shellfish, in Aberdeen, UK.

3.5.3. Aquaculture Europe 2023

Aquaculture Europe 2023, set in Vienna, served as an ideal platform to showcase GRINNAQUA and interact with professionals, researchers, and enthusiasts in the aquaculture industry. Being part of the Blue Bio-Economy collaborative stand (Fig. 29) allowed permanent engagement with attendees, discussing research, innovations, and projects in the field of aquaculture. The team was also present with a poster (Fig. 30), providing a visual and detailed overview of the work in GRINNAQUA, sparking insightful discussions.

Fig. 29: GRINNAQUA information at the Blue BioEconomy Colab Collaborative stand.

Fig. 30: Project poster showcased at the event. The poster is available for download on the GRINNAQUA website, under resources.

4. Dissemination of results

4.1. Participation in international conferences

4.1.1. International Symposium on Fish Nutrition and Feeding 2024

The GRINNAQUA team has submitted an abstract for an oral presentation at the International Symposium on Fish Nutrition and Feeding 2024, which will take place in Puerto Vallarta, Mexico from 27 to 31 Ma 2024. The work is titled “Immunomodulatory effects of dietary methionine on rainbow trout following viral haemorrhagic septicaemia virus (VHSV)” and is the result of a

collaborative work between CIIMAR, CISA-INIA-CSIC and UEDIN partners. No decision has yet been communicated.

Results from GRINNAQUA will also be submitted to Aqua2024, taking place in Copenhagen on 26-30 August 2024 and the 2nd Aquatic Animal Health Symposium, on the 11th and 12th of November 2024.

4.2. Publications

One publication has been published with contributions from GRINNAQUA. However, it is not yet related to results from the project but a review paper, and will not be counted as one of the 3 peer reviewed paper proposed in the GA. The article has been added to the continuous report section in the EC platform:

Type: Article in journal

Title: Synopsis of the Species of Coccidians Reported in Marine Fish

Authors: Aurélia Saraiva, Jorge C. Eiras, Cristina Cruz & Raquel Xavier

Journal: Animals

Peer reviewed: Yes

Open access: Yes

DOI: [10.3390/ani13132119](https://doi.org/10.3390/ani13132119)

[The Grant Agreement mentions in different pages that 3 or 4 publications will be produced in the context of GRINNAQUA. The correct number is 3, as the plan is to have one publication per task/subtask in WP3. The results for the first manuscript are currently under analysis. This manuscript will be prepared before the end of 2024. Manuscripts 2 and 3 will be released in 2025. All manuscripts will be submitted in specialized journals such as Frontiers in Immunology, Fish & Shellfish Immunology and Aquaculture.](#)

5. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The KPIs have been defined in Deliverable 6.1: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan.

KPI	Desired outcome	Performance measure
KPI 1: Number of applications, from academia and industry, in the workshops organized in the context of GRINNAQUA.	Receive enough applications to fill in all spots available	1st workshop: 47 applications. For 30 spots.
		2nd workshop: 58 applications, 5 from the aquaculture industry, for 30 spots. 12 extra were accepted for the theoretical session only.
KPI 2: Evaluation by participants of the workshop lectures in relation to their initial expectations – questionnaires.	Receive and average feedback for the workshop organization and content of excellent	Overall, participants were very pleased with the quality of the workshops, rating it as excellent.
KPI 3: Number of participants or individuals enrolled (in case of limited participation) in the two summer schools.	No summer schools have taken place yet, per the project plan	
KPI 4: Evaluation by participants of the summer school on their improved skills and knowledge – questionnaires.		
KPI 5: Number of people involved in staff exchange initiatives.	6 PhD student exchanges	4 PhD student exchanges: 1 to CISA-INIA-CSIC and 3 to Roslin/UEDIN.
	7 Technical staff	3 technical staff exchanges, to UiB.
	2 Administrative Staff	1 administrative staff exchange.
KPI 6: Evaluation by the staff on the skills, knowledge and networking gained from the exchange – questionnaires.	Receive and average feedback of excellent	All personnel involved have rated the staff exchanges as excellent in terms of knowledge and skills gained. For more details on staff exchange, please see Deliverable 4.3.
KPI 7: Subscriptions to project newsletter, taking into consideration if the subscribers	50 subscribers, GRINNAQUA members	GRINNAQUA currently has 53 newsletter subscribers, 16 of which are members of GRINNAQUA. The newsletter has,

are part of the project or external.	amounting to less than 40% after 1 year. 50% increase by the end of the project	however, been reaching many subscribers as non-subscribers.
KPI 8: Number of project-related social media posts.	One post per week, on average. At least 50% of which original posts.	Most posts are duplicated on the two social media platforms. The team has published 89 posts on Twitter, 45 of which are original.
KPI 9: Social media reach. Number of visualizations per post (average) throughout the project.	Reach on average 500 accounts on Twitter and 200 accounts on LinkedIn on average, after 1 year. Achieve a 50% increase each year	Original posts are currently reaching, on average, around 300 accounts on Twitter and 2 000 on LinkedIn.
KPI 10: Participation in events. National / International. Size of the event.	10 International events 6 National events	National Academia/students: one event. No information on the number of participants General public: one event, 12 participants Industry: two events, around 100 people in each. International 3 events with several hundred participants each
KPI 11: Number of submitted projects and fellowships. National / International.	3 Horizon Europe	5 Horizon Europe 1 Blue Partnership 2 National Please see deliverable 5.1 for more information

<p>KPI 12: Business stakeholder involvement through questionnaires.</p>	<p>20 stakeholders involved</p>	<p>4 stakeholders. These efforts have not been as successful as the team hoped due to diverse constraints. A new strategy has been devised. Please see Deliverable 2.3 for more details.</p>
<p>KPI 13: CIIMAR's publication rate, in aquaculture and animal health.</p>	<p>15 publications per year by the A2S team</p>	<p>Since November 2022, the team has published 25 peer-reviewed papers, 2 books and 1 book chapter in aquaculture and animal health (avg 19/year). Information at CIIMAR level has not been gathered at this point.</p>
<p>KPI 14: Impact factor of publications.</p>	<p>We should abandon this KPI as it doesn't reflect well the relevance of the work</p>	
<p>KPI 15: Participation in talent recruitment initiatives.</p>	<p>1 MSCA IF 1 MSCA ITN</p>	<p>One international initiative: La Caixa fellowships. Two Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions applications</p>
<p>KPI 16: Involvement in European aquaculture platforms/consortia.</p>	<p>One new platform and 1 international consortia</p>	<p>Built from GRINNAQUA, a new consortia with 17 partners has received funding. GRINNAQUA is now part of an aquaculture and animal health project cluster</p>

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